

Women Scientists of the Indian Space Research Organisation

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A B S T R A C T

The ISRO (Indian Space Research Organisation) established 15th August 1969 by the founding father of space program in India Dr. Vikram A. Sarabhai was brought under the department of space setup in 1st June 1972 with a prime objective to develop a space technology and apply it to various national needs. ISRO has developed two satellite launch vehicle namely PSLV and GSLV to place the INSAT and the IRS in the respective orbits. The contribution of ISRO for over 5 decades to the scientific community is a pride to the nation. The super powers are perplexed to note the astonishing development of the ISRO to the level of launch of the Chandrayaan – 3 especially at a lesser cost. India a country which has a history of gender discrimination in its social organisation has evolved in to a women empowered society. This track of development is evident by the tremendous contributions and performance of excellence by eminent women scientist of ISRO. This study is to limelight the contributions of some of them and their mile stone achievements and contributions for the overall excellence of ISRO in the international arena.

Key Words: ISRO, Space, Orbit, PSLV, GSLV. National Committee.

Introduction

Indian National Committee for Space Research (INCOSPAR) was setup by the government of India in 1962 as envisioned by Dr. Vikram A. Sarabhai. Later on August 15 1969 the INCOSPAR was super seeded by ISRO with an aim to play an expanded role involving Science, Engineering and Technology to harness the benefits of outer space technology for the benefit of the country and mankind. Subsequently in 1972 the DOS (Department of Space) was established and ISRO was under its control.

The prime objective of ISRO is development and application of space technology by establishing major space systems the communication, television broadcasting, meteorological services, resource monitoring and management; space based navigation services satellite launch vehicles such as PSLV (Polar Launch Vehicle) and GSLV (Geosynchronous Launch Vehicle) to place satellites in the prescribed orbits. Further the ISRO contributes to science education were-in various dedicated research centres and autonomous institutions for remote sensing and astronomy Astro-Physics atmospheric sciences and space sciences are in vogue under the aegis of the Department of Space. The lunar and interplanetary missions such as *Chandrayaan* and *Mangalyaan* provide valuable data to the scientific community which enriches the science on the whole. Since inception the Indian Space Program had three distinct elements such as satellites for communication and remote sensing; the space transportation system and application programmes. In 1967 the first experimental satellite communication earth station (ESCES) in Ahmadabad was operationalised which later came a training centre for Indian and international scientist. Bangalore is the head quarters of ISRO. The Vikram Sarabai Space Centre VSSC at Thiruvananthapuram builds the launch vehicles. The U.R.Rao Satellite Centres (URSC) at Bangalore designs and develops satellites. The Satish Dhawan Space Centre (SDSC) at Sriharikota integrates and launches satellites. The Liquid Propulsion Systems Centre (LPSC) at Valiamala and Bangalore develops various stages of liquid propulsion including Cryogenic stage. The Space Application Centre (SAC) at Ahmadabad takes care of sensors for communication and remote sensing satellite and application aspects of space technology. The National Remote Sensing Centre (NRSC) at Hyderabad is entrusted remote sensing satellite data processing and dissemination.

Women Scientist of ISRO

The Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) has taken India to great heights, its latest achievement being a soft landing at the south pole of the moon, a world record. On par the organisation has also uplifted women, signaling a social revolution in conservative India where the home is thought to be the ideal place for women. News agency IANS reported that as many as 54 women scientists and engineers were involved in the “Chandrayaan 3” project. An earlier BBC report quoted a lady Mission Director, Anuradha T. K., as saying that anywhere between 20 to 25% of ISRO’s 16,000 employees are women. At least eight women have been at the helm of projects as Directors and Deputy Directors, including in those projects sending probes to the moon and Mars. These women are fondly described as the “Rocket Women of India”. Director-level women have put in 30-plus years participating in multiple missions. By the way women have come up in ISRO since the 1980s, it is apparent that gender equality has been one of its defining values. Here are some of the notable female scientists and engineers who have worked with ISRO. These are just a few of the many female scientists and engineers who have worked with ISRO. They have made significant contributions to India's space program and have paved the way for more women to enter the field of space science. These ISRO scientists have dedicated their whole lives to Indian advancement in Space, even at the cost of their personal lives.

1. Ritu Karidhal Srivastava previously served as the Deputy Operations Director for the Mars Orbiter Mission. She is also known as the Rocket Women of India and she manages her role as a mother of two alongside her responsibilities at home and ISRO. Her Multitasking abilities are commendable. She has authored several research papers as a space scientist¹

2. Nandini Harinath realized her dream of becoming a scientist at a very young age and started her career with ISRO she served as the Deputy Director of the ISRO and remained active in the *Mangalyaan* mission²

3. Moumita Dutta an M Tech in Experimental Physics from Kolkatha University worked as a project manager for the *Mangalyaan* mission and actively participates in the *Make In India* campaign.³

4. Anuradha T.K. was appointed as the Director of Geosynchronous Satellite Launch Vehicle - 12 in 2011 she led a group of 20 members and achieved several technical successes. With her logical thinking she is an inspiration for other female scientists of the ISRO she has received **Suman Sharma Award**⁴

5. Minal Rohit started her career as a Satellite Communications engineer at Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO) and went on to work for the Space Application Center. She was one of 500 scientists and engineers who worked on the Mars Orbiter Mission. As Systems Engineer for the mission, she helped integrate and test the sensors that the orbiter was carrying **She abstained from taking any leaves for two years.** Rohit was a head engineer and a Project Manager for Chandrayaan II.⁵

6. Tessy Thomas played a crucial role in the success of *Agni-4* and *Agni-5* missiles Her contribution earned India a special place among countries with ICBMs She is called as “*Agni Poutri*” (*Daughter of Agni*)⁶

7. N. Valarmathi represented India as the Chief of the Indigenous Radar Imaging Satellite RISAT Mission and holds the record for being the Chief of the Remote Sensing Satellite Mission⁷

8. V. R. Lalithambika was a control systems engineer who played a key role in the development of India's first launch vehicle, SLV-3.⁸

9. Kushboo Mirza a citizen of the state of UP is part of the Indian Space Research Organisation's (ISRO) Chandrayan-3 mission that landed softly on the moon last Wednesday. Mirza comes from a humble family in Amroha, in western UP. At ISRO she is part of the team that built the equipment and software to receive data from the satellite that has landed on the moon. Today Mirza is a role model for many little girls in Amroha, all of whom want to grow up and be a scientist like her

10. Mangala mani a 56 year old was part of a team of 23 of Indian researchers in Antarctica in 2016 she was the only woman in the team and she spent more than 403 days in Antarctica

11. Muthayya Vanitha has worked at ISRO for over three decades. She joined the ISRO as a junior engineer working in various areas of hardware testing and development. She later succeeded to managerial positions, leading the Telemetry and Tele-command Divisions in the Digital Systems Group of ISRO Satellite Centre. She has also acted as deputy project director for several satellites including Cartosat-1, Oceansat-2, and Megha-Tropiques, where she was responsible for data operations. Vanitha was also involved in the successful Mangalyaan mission to Mars in 2013. She is also the first woman project director at ISRO. Mylswamy Annadurai, who convinced her to take on the role, said that her data handling, team management and problem solving skills made her the ideal person for this position. Vanitha's responsibilities include ensuring complete oversight of the development and implementation of all systems and acting as a point of authority for the project.⁹

12. Kriti Faujdar is known as a computer scientist at ISRO she excels in setting satellites in their correct orbits and is part of the team that keeps a close eye on satellites and other missions. The Master Control Facility (MCF) at Hassan, where she works, is one of the two facilities (the other is in Bhopal) that ISRO has tasked with monitoring its geostationary satellites like the INSATs, GSATs and Indian Regional Navigation Satellites System (IRNSS; now called Navigation with Indian Constellation, NAVIC). Such satellites orbit Earth at about 36,000 km from the surface. They rotate in sync with Earth's rotation, making them look stationary. Their ability to track the same spot for extended periods of time makes them invaluable for weather and communication purposes. Kriti and the rest of the MCF team have to make sure the satellites remain healthy and are not veered off-course by gravitational forces of the sun or moon.

These women are like ordinary women around us but their strong determination and desire to achieve something extraordinary have taken them to great heights even reaching for the sky. The contributions of the Women Scientists to the ISRO is commendable they have excelled in their fields their excellence have been rewarded in the form of special awards and titles

Gender Equality in ISRO

Gender equality is a human right, and according to the United Nations (UN), it is very essential to ensure sustainable development and to maintain peace around the world. Diversity is

essential to deliver excellence in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). Encouraging greater diversity allows scientific organisations to derive an “innovation dividend” that leads to a smarter, more creative teams, hence opening the door to new discoveries. Greater gender equality in STEM is crucial, and in the larger interest of scientific progress and society. Currently, India is looking at a paradoxical situation where women are studying STEM subjects but there are not as many women in STEM careers. The latest All-India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE) report suggests that India’s gender gap has narrowed in comparison with the past few years. Female students now constitute almost half (48.6%) of the total enrolment in higher education. The Government of India’s initiatives for gender advancement and equality in academic and research institutions are helping women succeed in STEM fields.¹⁰ Despite facing challenges, women in India are moving up the academic and administrative ladder by breaking down both systemic and structural barriers to excel in STEM. However, women constitute only 14% of the 280,000 personnel in STEM in India’s research development institutions (UN data). In addition, although women’s participation in the workforce is higher at entry-level, it gradually decreases at higher research, academics and administration levels.

“There is no gender discrimination in ISRO. Recruitment and promotional policies are all dependent on what we know and what we contribute” SAYS A WOMEN Scientist of ISRO. Only 8% of ISRO's scientific and technical staff make up of women. Sadly, no woman has headed it since it was founded in 1963. Women scientists say even when women are enrolled in PG and PhD in greater numbers, they fail to convert their degrees into careers due to the biological clock and family pressures. At work during missions, they may have to spend sleepless nights. Problems encountered have to be solved as quickly as possible. *“its very difficult to strike balance between work and home. But I feel that with meticulous planning both work and home can be managed”*, said one of the female scientists. Their brilliance and knowledge have captivated the world.

Conclusion

Equal representation alone will not guarantee achieving gender equality. A framework can set gender equality benchmarks by collecting qualitative data to determine if barriers exist and what actions could be introduced to tackle them. These qualitative criteria can range from

promotion of inclusive practices in the workplace to increase retention of women in STEM careers to creating support structures for career progression for women scientists. Besides helping institutions improve gender equality, such a framework can also assist institutions in meeting requirements and expectations of national and international funders and research councils.

The UK has pioneered the Athena SWAN Gender Equality Charter and the Accreditation System which started in 2005. Recognising the evidence-based approach to research, intervention and demonstrable effects of the framework, many countries have joined the Athena SWAN collaborative international network, including United States, Australia, Canada, Ireland. With the launch of Gender Advancement for Transforming Institutions (GATI), India too has joined the list. While learning from and the success of Athena SWAN, it is focused on the Indian context and realities. The Department of Science and Technology has undertaken the programme in partnership with the British Council. Key elements of the project include capacity-building through training and supporting participating institutions in self-assessment through collaboration with Athena Swan-awarded UK institutions in their gender equality journey.

Gender Equality frameworks such as GATI will bring about a shift in approach in technical institutions and will also inspire senior leaders to take every possible action to attract, hire, retain and promote more women in India's STEM fields. While India has been making strides in this space in terms of a more equitable enrolment ratio, a gender equality framework for higher education institutions will translate into India achieving a substantial milestone. This will not only be consistent with the ambitious goals of NEP 2020 but also be crucial in aligning to United Nations Sustainable Development Goal.

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